

18TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS
SURFACE FUNCTIONALIZATION OF MULTI-WALLED CARBON

NANOTUBES WITH RANDOM COPOLYMER:

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION

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Abstract

The copolymer poly (thiophene ethanol-co-hexyl thiophene) (P3ET-co-P3HT) and its composites with multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) were prepared via in-situ oxidative polymerization. The functionalization of MWNTs was achieved by introducing active sites (-COOH) onto the surface of MWNTs by oxidizing them with the mixture of H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ (1:3). The oxidized MWNTs were reacted subsequently with SOCl₂ to get acylated MWNTs. The acylated MWNTs were grafted with 3-thiophene ethanol via “ester linkage” followed by copolymerization with 3-hexyl thiophene using anhydrous FeCl₃ as an oxidizing agent. The structure and morphology of the nanocomposites were characterized by FTIR, XPS, TGA, HR-TEM and FE-SEM. The doping function of MWNTs in the composites was analyzed using UV-vis and PL spectroscopy. Morphological observations revealed that the functionalized MWNTs were uniformly dispersed in the copolymer matrix. UV-Vis spectra showed that the absorption peak of the copolymer was red-shifted by 20nm. The emission spectra indicated that the PL intensity of the nanocomposites was much higher than that of the copolymer.

1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have various applications in many fields of nanotechnology due to their unique mechanical, thermal, and electrical properties [1]. This wide range of properties makes CNTs potentially attractive tools for a variety of applications, from nanoelectronics to biomedical devices [2–4]. The effective utilization of CNTs in nanocomposite applications depends strongly on the ability to disperse CNTs homogeneously throughout a matrix without destroying the integrity of CNTs. However, the practical applications of CNTs are impeded by their tendency to agglomerate and their insolubilities in organic solvents and water [5]. Surface functionalization of CNTs has been actively pursued, which is crucial for preventing the

aggregation of CNTs in solutions or polymer matrices and fully utilizing their unique properties. Various approaches have been developed for enhancing dispersion, including covalent sidewall functionalization of CNTs [6], noncovalent sidewall functionalization of CNTs [7] in situ polymerization of monomers with nanotubes [8] polymer wrapping [9] and solution blending [10]. In particular, surface functionalization of CNTs either covalent or non-covalent functionalization is one of the major techniques developed to improve the CNT dispersion or solubilization. It involves the physical adsorption of polymers or surfactants on the nanotube surface [11].

In recent years, polymeric materials and their composites with CNTs have found extensive applications in organic electronics [12,13]. The formation of CNTs/polymer composites has been explored for possible improvement in the electrical and mechanical properties of polymers. In particular, composite materials based on the coupling of conducting polymers and CNTs have been shown to possess properties of the individual components with a synergistic effect. CNTs can be used as ideal reinforcing agents for high performance polymer composites. Numerous molecular electronic devices, including light-emitting diodes [14] photovoltaic cells [15] transistors [16] sensors [17] and memories [18] have been demonstrated.

In this article, we report a new strategy for the synthesis of nanocomposites consisting of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNTs) with a random copolymer poly (3-thiophene ethanol-co-hexylthiophene) (P3ET-co-P3HT). The MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites were prepared via in-situ oxidative polymerization in the presence of functionalized MWNTs. The structure and morphology of the resulting MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites were investigated in detail using FTIR, XPS, HRTEM, XRD, FT-IR, UV-vis and PL spectroscopy.

2 Experimental details

2.1 Materials

MWNTs (ca. 90% purity) with a diameter range of 10-20 nm were obtained from Iljin Nanotech Co. Ltd (Korea). 3ET and 3HT were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Korea) and used as received. Anhydrous CHCl_3 and methanol were obtained from Junsei (Japan) and distilled before use.

2.2 Purification of MWNTs

Pristine MWNTs were purified by thermal and acid treatment. The pristine MWNTs were heated in air at 650°C for 2h, and then cooled and refluxed with conc. HCl for 24h. After the mixture was diluted with de-ionized water, the precipitate was collected and washed repeatedly with distilled water. The product was filtered and dried in a vacuum oven for 12 h at 40°C .

2.3 Surface functionalization of MWNTs

1.0 g of purified MWNTs were suspended in 150 mL of the mixture of conc. H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 (1:3 v/v), and the dispersion was sonicated at room temperature for 8 h. The mixture was diluted with 300 mL of de-ionized water and filtered through a 0.1mM polytetrafluoroethylene filter membrane. The filtered product (MWNTs-COOH) was washed with distilled water until the pH value of the filtrate became neutral.

2.4 Acylation of MWNTs

MWNTs-COOH (0.6 mg), was reacted with 100 mL of SOCl_2 at 70°C for 24 h under reflux to convert the surface-bound -COOH groups into acyl chloride groups. Any residual SOCl_2 was removed by rotary evaporation, and the solids that were subsequently obtained were filtered and washed with anhydrous THF. Lastly, the filtrate was dried under vacuum at room temperature for 4 h to give acyl chloride functionalized MWNTs (MWNTs-COCl).

2.5 Preparation of MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT)

Scheme 1 shows the chemical reactions used for the preparation of the MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites. In a typical experiment, 0.5 g of MWNTs-COCl was added into 50 mL of CHCl_3 and sonicated for 30 min. 0.25 g of 3-ET was added dropwise to the mixture. 0.25 g of 3-HT and 2 g of anhydrous FeCl_3 were added into the above mixture.

The reaction mixture was stirred continuously under a nitrogen atmosphere at room temperature for 24 h. After polymerization, the reaction mixture was poured into 200 mL methanol in order to remove the ungrafted polymers and FeCl_3 . The precipitate was washed several times with acetone to minimize the FeCl_3 content in the composites and the composites were dried in a vacuum oven at 50°C . The copolymer was synthesized with the same procedure for the comparison.

2.6 Characterization

FT-IR analysis of the MWNT-COOH and MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites was done using Perkin-Elmer GX (USA) in the frequency range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The FTIR measurements of the powder samples were performed in the form of KBr pellets. XRD measurements were performed in the 2θ region on a Rigaku diffractometer using nickel-filtered $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation. The morphologies of the nanocomposites were examined by using a transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEOL JEM-2000EX) and a field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) equipped with in situ energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectra (Hitachi, S-2700 model microscope, Japan). Samples for TEM were deposited onto carbon-coated copper electron microscope grids and dried in air. Thermal study of the composites was studied using Thermo gravimetric analysis (Perkin Elmer) Pyris1 at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ under nitrogen atmosphere. The chemical structure of the composites was carried out on a ESCA 2000 XPS (Thermo VG Scientific) using a monochromatic ($\text{Mg KR} = 1253.6\text{ eV}$) source. UV-visible spectra were obtained using a Perkin Elmer Lambda 40 ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectrometer. PL spectra were recorded on a F-4500 spectrofluorometer (Hitachi, Japan).

3 Results and discussion

FT-IR spectra were used to characterize the functional groups of polymers and MWNTs after modification. Fig.1 shows the FTIR spectra of the oxidized MWNTs, pure copolymer and composites. The functionalized MWNTs (Fig.1a) showed a strong peak at 3400 cm^{-1} due to the OH stretching mode of the COOH group. A sharp peak at 1740 cm^{-1} was assigned to the C=O stretching vibration, suggesting the formation of COOH groups on MWNTs. The characteristic peaks at 1550 and

1220 cm^{-1} , could be attributed to the C=C and C–O stretching modes of the graphitic structure, respectively [19]. The pristine (P3ET-co-P3HT) exhibited some characteristic absorption peaks at 2950–2850 cm^{-1} (aliphatic C–H stretch), 1500 cm^{-1} (ring stretch), 1420 cm^{-1} (methyl deformation), 1120 cm^{-1} (C–O stretch) and 820 cm^{-1} (aromatic C–H out-of-plane vibrations), while the FTIR spectrum of the composites showed the complete disappearance of the O–H stretching vibration and the appearance of the C=O stretching band 1730 cm^{-1} . The weak shoulder at 720 cm^{-1} observed for both the copolymer and composites due to the C–S–C ring deformation.

XPS is one of the surface analytical techniques, which could provide useful information on the nature of the functional groups on the MWNT surface. Fig. 2A shows the XPS spectra of the pristine, MWNT-COOH and MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites. The XPS spectra of the pristine and functionalized MWNTs exhibited a major peak at 284.5 eV and a trace level peak 533.5 eV corresponding to the graphite carbon (sp²) and oxygen functionalities, respectively. Fig.2 (B&C). shows the C1s spectra of the pristine and oxidized MWNTs. The C1s spectra of the pristine and MWNT-COOH, which could be resolved into five characteristic peaks. The binding energies of 284.7 eV, 286.4 eV, 288.3 eV, 289.9 eV, and 291.6 eV were attributed to C–C, C–O, C=O, O=C–O and π - π^* respectively [20]. However, the oxygen content in the MWNT-COOH was much higher than that of the pristine MWNTs due to the effective oxidation process. In the case of the composites, C1s and O1s peaks were observed with an additional peak at 164 eV due to the neutral sulphur atom. It could be clearly seen that the S2s and S2p signals were totally absent in the case of pristine MWNT and MWNT-COOH, as they appeared in the composites. The S2p core-level spectrum (Fig.3D) of the MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites could be deconvoluted into at least two spin-orbit-split doublet (S2p_{3/2} and S 2p_{1/2}) peaks at approximately 164.1 and 165 eV, which were attributed to the neutral sulphur atoms, respectively [21]. These results were further supported by the EDX analysis. Fig.3 shows the EDX spectrum of the composites. The EDX spectrum strongly revealed the presence of sulfur in the nanocomposites, which originated from the copolymer matrix.

Fig.4 shows the TGA spectra of the pristine MWNTs, MWNT-COOH, MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites and copolymer. Pristine MWNTs did not show any significant weight loss below 700°C. On the contrary, MWNT-COOH decomposed gradually with increasing temperature arising from the loss of carboxyl groups on the surface of MWNTs. The copolymer (P3ET-co-P3HT) started to lose the weight at 370°C, and was completely decomposed by 460°C. However, the nanocomposites showed the similar TGA profile to that of the copolymer. For the composites, the weight loss between 370 and 460°C could be attributed to the decomposition of the grafted polymer. As shown in Fig.5c, the copolymer content in the nanocomposites was calculated to be 30% by TGA.

The morphology of the pristine MWNTs, MWNTs-COOH, and MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites are shown in Fig.5. The MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites (Fig.5c&d) showed a major change in the morphology and structure in comparison to the pristine MWNTs (Fig.5a) and MWNT-COOH (Fig.6b). The pristine MWNTs showed snake-like shape morphology with a smooth surface. After acid-oxidation, the end tips of many MWNTs were opened (Fig.5b), indicating the breaking of the C–C bond along the graphene layers of the co-axial tubes and thus allowing for the generation of functional groups at the open ends [22]. However, the morphology of the composites showed that the individual MWNTs were coated with polymer chains and the external diameters of the composites increased substantially when compared with the pristine and MWNTs-COOH. SEM observation clearly showed the uniform distribution of MWNTs in the copolymer matrices. This is further confirmed by the observation using HR-TEM. TEM images of the pristine MWNTs and the MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites are shown in Fig 6. The pristine MWNTs showed the smooth surfaces without detectable polymer layer. However, after the copolymer was covalently grafted onto MWNTs, a core-shell nanostructure consisting of a MWNTs core and a polymer outer shell could be observed from the Fig 6(b&c). It could be clearly seen that the outer surfaces of MWNTs were fully coated with a thin polymer layer and its external diameter ranges from 20–30 nm depending on the un-uniformed polymer layer. TEM

images of nanocomposites revealed that the surface of the MWNTs was found to be wrapped by an uneven layer of copolymer, indicating that the copolymer was successfully grafted on the surfaces of MWNTs.

XRD spectra of MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites and pure P3ET-co-P3HT are shown in Fig 7. XRD pattern of MWNTs-COOH revealed the presence of two peaks at 25.7 and 43.6°, corresponding to the interlayer spacing (0.34 nm) of the MWNTs (d_{002}) and the d_{100} reflection of the MWNTs, respectively, in good agreement with the literature [23]. Meanwhile, the copolymer showed a broad peak at 24°, confirmed the amorphous feature of the copolymer. However, the XRD pattern of the composites exhibited the similar to those observed from the pure copolymer matrix, indicating that no additional crystalline order or chain arrangement had been introduced into the composites. This result revealed that there was a very thin copolymer layer coated on the surface of MWNTs.

The UV-vis absorption spectra and PL spectra could provide a good deal of information on the electronic structures of the conjugated polymers and its composites. The absorption spectra of the pure P3ET-co-P3HT and the MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites in dichlorobenzene are shown in Fig.8. As can be seen, the pure copolymer showed an absorption peak at 430 nm, corresponding to the π - π^* transition of the conjugated polythiophene segments. On the addition of MWNTs, this band was red-shifted by 20 nm, suggesting a decrease in band gap. The red -shift in the UV absorption peak probably originates from the result of the strong interactions between the copolymer chains and nanotubes, which uncoils the copolymer chains, thereby increasing their conjugation length [24].

The PL spectra of the pure copolymer and its composites were studied in the wavelength range 450–700 nm. The PL spectra of the copolymer and the nanocomposites are shown in Fig.9. The copolymer exhibited an emission in the blue spectral region with maximum at 575 nm, while the nanocomposites showed the emission peak at 580 nm. However, the PL intensity of the copolymer was greatly enhanced by the addition of MWNTs. Generally, MWNTs do not show any significant PL quenching at this wavelength range [25]. Therefore, the sharp increase of PL intensity indicated the

strong interactions between the excited state of the copolymer and the MWNTs.

4 Conclusions

The copolymer P3ET-co-P3HT and its composites with functionalized MWNTs were prepared via in-situ oxidative polymerization. The nanocomposites were characterized by FTIR, XPS, TGA, FESEM and HRTEM. The doping function of MWNTs in the composites was proved by UV-vis and PL spectroscopy. SEM observations indicated that the MWNTs were well dispersed in the copolymer matrices. TEM observation revealed that the nanocomposites showed the core-shell structure and the outer surfaces of MWNTs were wrapped with the thin copolymer layers. UV-Vis spectra indicated that the absorption peak of the copolymer was red-shifted by 15nm. The emission spectra showed that the PL intensity of the copolymer was enhanced significantly after incorporation of the MWNTs.

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5 Figures

Scheme 1: Reaction scheme for grafting of P3ET-co-P3HT chains onto MWNTs.

Figure 1: FTIR spectra of A) MWNTs-COOH B) MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites and C) (P3ET-co-P3HT)

Figure 2: XPS spectra of MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites C1s core level spectra of B) pristine MWNTs C) MWNTs-COOH and D) S2p core level spectrum of MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites

Figure 3: EDX spectra of the MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites

Figure 4: TGA of A) pristine MWNTs B) MWNTs-COOH C) MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites and D) (P3ET-co-P3HT)

Figure 5: FESEM images of A) pristine MWNTs B) MWNTs-COOH C) and C) MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites.

Figure 6: HRTEM images of A) pristine MWNTs and B) & C) MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites under different magnifications.

Figure 7: XRD patterns of A) MWNTs-COOH B) MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites and C) (P3ET-co-P3HT)

Figure 8: UV-Vis spectra of A) (P3ET-co-P3HT) and B) MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites

Figure 9: PL spectra of A) (P3ET-co-P3HT) and B) MWNTs-g-(P3ET-co-P3HT) composites

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